

NOTES

Scheme 1

Synthesis of some Bis-thiosemicarbazones and their related 1,3,4-Thiadiazolines

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDE derivatives are well-known for their biological activities¹. Many thiadiazoles also possess antibacterial and antitubercular activities². Some patented materials derive from methylenedianiline (MDA) are active insecticidal and fungicidal agents³. MDA itself is also active antibacterial agents⁴. Keeping this in view, the titled compounds (2 and 3) have been prepared following the reported procedure⁵ (Scheme 1) and their antimicrobial activity was tested.

Results and Discussion

The compounds (Table 1) were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate method⁶ and screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain (A) of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v and the strain (B) isolated from the sputum of pulmonary tuberculosis patient using absolute concentration method⁷.

Antibacterial activity: Thiosemicarbazones show moderate antibacterial activity (zone diameter = 10 – 40 mm) against both the species. Compounds having phenyl, 2-hydroxyphenyl, 4-chlorophenyl, 4-nitrophenyl, 5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl and 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl substituents are active against both the species. Thiadiazoles show remarkable antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (zone dia. = 16 to >40 mm) and show poor activity against *E. coli* (zone dia. = 16 – 20 mm). Both the compounds (2 and 3) having 2-hydroxyphenyl, 5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl and 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl substituents show promising results against both the species.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THIOSEMICARBAZONES (2) AND 1,3,4-THIADIAZOLINES (3)*

Sl no	R	Mol formula	M p °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	2 C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₆ S ₂	212	70
		3 C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₆ S ₂	189	65
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₆ S ₂	218–20	72
		C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₆ S ₂	202	65
3	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	180	78
		C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	200–02	68
4	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	192	76
		C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	180	71
5.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ S ₂	176	73
		C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ S ₂	188	72

(Table 1 Contd.)

6.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2 C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	203-5	69
7.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂	161	62
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂	196	65
8.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂	176	67
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂	184	69
9.	4,N,N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ S ₂	206-8	68
		C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ S ₂	220	64
10.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	189-90	80
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	209	76
11.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	180	81
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	221	75
12.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	224	79
		C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	206	75
13.	5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	230	75
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	251	71
14.	3,5-(Br) ₂ -2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	218	73
		C ₂₀ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	262	76
15.	C ₄ H ₁₀	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	260d	71
		C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	340	67

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) **2** (R=C₆H₅), 1 180 (C=S), 3 300 (NH), 1 380 (C=N), 1 460 (CH₂), 840-820 and 760-760 cm⁻¹ (benzene ring); $\lambda_{\max}$ **2** (R=2-OH-C₆H₄), 217 and 315 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ **3** (R=C₆H₅), 3 220 (NH), 1 480 (C=N), 1 460 (CH₂), 840-820 and 780-60 cm⁻¹ (benzene ring); $\lambda_{\max}$ **3** (R=2-OH-C₆H₄), 223, 283 and 315 nm.

Antitubercular activity: Compounds **2** and **3** were found to be more active against H₃₇R_v (A) and less active against a typical strain (B). But the overall antitubercular activity is very poor and compounds having 4-hydroxyphenyl substituents was found active at 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, but inactive at 150 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level.

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